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- ❖ **India's Strategic Outreach to Sri Lanka**
- ❖ **Trump, Tariff and BRICS**
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Unrelenting Conflict and Humanitarian Crisis in Gaza

It's almost 22 months by now since Israel commenced its military offensive against Gaza to wipe out Hamas, which it considers as a terrorist organization responsible for the escalation of the conflict. Prolonged conflict has brought untold and tremendous misery to the innocent population of Gaza Strip for no fault of theirs. Israel claims the death of civilians that includes women and children as collateral damage owing to its offensive against Hamas, which it vows to liquidate for all time to come.

Israeli forces began airstrikes and ground military operations after Hamas and other armed groups launched a deadly ground incursion and rocket barrage on southern Israel. Reportedly, both Hamas and Israel have been holding number of hostages and are still trying to bargain with each other. It may be difficult to brand any of the warring parties as 'war criminal'; but fact remains that their act may contribute towards criminalizing the future generations who have lost their near and dear ones for no fault of their own. The extent of fire power used by Israel in Gaza has been massive and beyond proportion precipitating humanitarian crisis of unprecedented proportion.

Gaza has a population of 2.1 million people. Reportedly 470,000 people face mass starvation in different parts of Gaza. 90 percent of the entire population that includes more than 762,500 stands displaced. More than 61,000 people have died and nearly 151,000 have been injured in Gaza alone since October 2023. Though, the figure may vary according to different sources. More than 70% of the entire infrastructure stands devastated and destroyed. Children, pregnant women and the elderly are being treated in hospitals for severe malnutrition with bare minimum infrastructure. Gaza strip has been in international news since long for all the wrong reasons. Once again it is experiencing humanitarian crisis on account of the military offensive being waged by its arch rival Israel. Different international media have been carrying the news of ever-escalating crisis and its worsening situation day-by-day. Crisis is being evident mostly in terms of famine, hunger and healthcare collapse alongside massive devastation of its infrastructure. Families are entrapped as shelling continues thereby grounding the residential structures and other buildings in the region.

Pregnant women, new mothers and newborns are worst affected lot. Reportedly, for 180 women who are suppose to give birth daily; accessing healthcare is an unimaginable challenge. Hence, donations from all over the world are being sought for them by concerned international organizations. Small little children are dying of malnutrition, which is catastrophic. Humanitarian and medical needs are mostly unmet as only 12 per cent of the Strip consists of 'Safe Zones' now. Israel has been increasingly tightening its blockade around Gaza Strip which is leading to increased shortages of fuel, food, medicine, water and all other supplies which are deemed essential, as bare minimum for sustenance of life and livelihood. Electricity availability has dropped by 90% which is essential for hospital and other healthcare related services including sewage plants and drinking water supply. Thus, one can only imagine the scale and extend of devastation in Gaza Strip and the impending crisis amidst the escalation of conflict. According to IPC (Integrated Food Security Phase Classification); an UN-backed system for assessing and communicating food insecurity and famine risk, parts of Gaza are under catastrophic spell of famine. United Nations World Food Programme Palestine is very much on the ground in Gaza and West Bank. The officials and volunteers are contributing their best by distributing food and other helps but are fast depleting and proving highly inadequate, as most families are relying entirely on such food aid to survive. Israel's aid for Gaza has earned a bad name for its notoriety, as allegedly Israel resorted to firing on the innocent people who queue-up for collecting food and other available essentials. Thus, Israel's aid has come as a deterrent for life of innocent civilians.

Crisis that has erupted in Gaza is scheduled to continue for generations to come. It speaks volume about the softness and futility of International Humanitarian Law. The long-term effects of chronic malnutrition and dwindling healthcare will echo far into the future. Disruptions have precipitated shortages of essential supplies necessary to survive. Death of children on account of hunger and malnutrition are heart renting, for which the international community and global leadership will never be forgiven. It's not a disaster in the making; rather it is there on the ground in Gaza and replete on our television screens, which calls for immediate action and aid interventions. Red Cross, Red Crescent or United Nations may not be able to handle the same without support from major powers of the world. Action or inaction, is going to be the test of our shared humanity, a test that international community cannot afford to fail or forget.

—BK

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India's Strategic Outreach to Sri Lanka

Dr. Rohil Oberoi* & Ms. Dikumoni Hazarika**

[This paper's primary objective is to analyze the evolution of India-Sri Lanka relations under Prime Minister Narendra Modi's 'Neighbourhood First' policy. It examines how New Delhi's engagement has evolved from traditional ties to a dynamic, multifaceted partnership, with a particular focus on India's proactive diplomacy and its crucial role as the 'first responder' during Sri Lanka's 2022 economic crisis. The analysis also assesses how this relationship has been shaped by the strategic imperative to navigate China's growing influence, ultimately highlighting how crisis-driven cooperation and a renewed focus on trade, infrastructure, connectivity, and defense have defined this evolving bilateral relationship in the contemporary era.]

India's strategic location in South Asia, bordered by Pakistan, China, Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh, Myanmar, and Sri Lanka, provides the foundation for a complex and dynamic network of connections with its neighbours. This geographical position influences India's diplomatic, economic, and security engagements in the region. India's 'Neighbourhood First' Policy (NFP), also known as the *South Asian Foreign Policy (SAFP)*, focuses on developing ties with neighbouring South Asian countries. This strategy aims to improve regional peace and cooperation by promoting trade, connectivity, and people-to-people exchanges with nations on India's periphery (Aryal & Bharti, 2023). According to the Ministry of External Affairs (Economic Diplomacy Division) brief, "India's 'Neighbourhood First' Policy rests on India's prime responsibility to lift its neighbours to establish a rules-based order to preserve multilateralism and to establish peace and security in the Indian Ocean" (Basrur, 2017). Three primary objectives were set for the 'Neighbourhood First' Policy under PM Modi: *Swabimaan (self-respect)*, *Suraksha (national security)*, and *Samvridi (economic growth and development)*. With these goals, India aims to enhance its international influence by strategically leveraging its regional ties (Viswapramod, 2024).

Sri Lanka is a very important neighbour of India. Its strategic location in the Indian Ocean, which serves as a hub for naval fleet movement between the Bay of Bengal and the Arabian Sea, makes it essential to

India's security interests. Moreover, the changing geopolitical landscape has had a significant impact on India-Sri Lanka ties, particularly in terms of maritime security, economic cooperation, and regional stability (Brewster, 2014). The Indian Ocean Region (IOR) is a major hub for global trade and energy supply lines, with important shipping lanes flowing through the region, including the Malacca Strait, the Gulf of Aden, and the Strait of Hormuz (Cordner, 2010). Sri Lanka's strategic location near these important marine lanes has made it a target for regional and extra-regional powers. India, with its historical and cultural ties to Sri Lanka, views the island nation as a key partner in ensuring regional peace and security. Therefore, Sri Lanka occupies a central position in India's 'Neighbourhood First' Policy and its broader vision of *Security and Growth for All in the Region (SAGAR)*.

Sri Lanka gained independence from British rule in 1948, a year after India's independence. Initially, relations were cordial, with both nations cooperating in regional matters. However, ethnic tensions between the Sinhalese majority and the Tamil minority in Sri Lanka led to political disputes. The 1954 Indo-Ceylon Agreement between Indian Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru and Sri Lankan Prime Minister Sir John Kotelawala aimed to address the issue of Indian-origin Tamils in Sri Lanka. A further agreement in 1964 (the Sirimavo-Shastri Pact) decided the repatriation of a section of Tamils to India while granting Sri Lankan citizenship to others. However, the Tamil issue caused tensions, particularly during the 1983–2009 civil war in Sri Lanka, in which India was a major player and sent

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the Indian Peace Keeping Force (IPKF) in 1987 (Gooneratne, 1998).

Sri Lanka's economic crisis, which began in 2019, remains one of the most difficult times in the country's history. A combination of economic mismanagement, external shocks, and fiscal deficiencies resulted in an unprecedented financial crisis. One of the most significant ways India helped Sri Lanka was with a \$4 billion line of credit given in 2022. This loan arrangement allowed Sri Lanka to buy essentials such as food, medicines, and fuel at a time when its foreign exchange reserves were almost depleted (Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2024).

A growing strategic and developmental partnership has been reflected in the high-level engagements that have taken place in recent years between India and Sri Lanka, including reciprocal visits by the two countries' presidents and prime ministers. Despite leading the traditionally pro-Chinese Janatha Vimukthi Peramuna (JVP) party, President Anura Kumara Disanayaka paid a state visit to India from December 15 to 17, 2024, marking his first journey abroad since taking office. President Anura Kumara Disanayaka was joined by Foreign Minister Vijitha Herath and Minister of Labour Anil Jayantha. During the visit, a joint statement entitled '*Fostering Partnerships for a Shared Future*' was released. During the visit, Dissanayake's explicit assurance that "*Sri Lanka will not permit its territory to be used in any manner inimical to India's security interests*". It directly addresses India's long-standing concerns about Chinese surveillance vessels docking in Sri Lankan ports and other security sensitivities. In April 2025, PM Modi paid a visit to the nation. His visit to Sri Lanka, at President Dissanayake's invitation, marked his fourth visit since 2015. With his visit to Sri Lanka, Prime Minister Modi is putting India's "*Vision Mahasagar (Ocean Vision)*" policies into action (Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2025). On April 5, 2025, Prime Minister Narendra Modi was greeted with full ceremonial honours in Colombo's historic Independence Square. According to PIB (2025), the two leaders opened the 128-kilometer Maho-Omanthai railway line, which was renovated with Indian aid of USD 91.27 million, as well as the

installation of a modern signalling system between Maho and Anuradhapura, which was funded by an Indian contribution of USD 14.89 million (Press Information Bureau, 2025).

In a remarkable gesture of gratitude, President Dissanayake presented PM Modi with Sri Lanka's highest civilian honour, the "*Mitra Vibhushana*," which is given to foreign leaders. Symbols such as the "*Dharma Chakra*," which symbolizes Buddhist history, the "*Pun Kalasa*," which signifies prosperity, and the "*Navaratna*," which consists of nine gems arranged within a globe and denotes enduring friendship, are included in the medal's design to express shared ideals. The gesture affirms India's acknowledged position as the "*big brother*" in the region and expresses gratitude for its support throughout the Sri Lankan economic crisis (Times of India, 2025).

After nearly three decades of domestic turmoil, Sri Lanka focused on economic recovery and a more Asia-centric foreign policy. These reforms resulted in a rebalancing of India-Sri Lanka bilateral relations, emphasizing their growing partnership in the region.

Strategic Trade and Economic Partnerships

The India-Sri Lanka Free Trade Agreement (ISFTA) is the relevant trade agreement between the two nations, in effect since 2000, and promotes bilateral trade. The merchandise trade between India and Sri Lanka reached USD 5.54 billion in FY 2023-24, with India exporting USD 4.11 billion and Sri Lanka exporting USD 1.42 billion. In the current fiscal year 2024-25, bilateral trade has reached USD 3.67 billion from April to November, with India's exports to Sri Lanka totaling USD 2.84 billion. In addition to being Sri Lanka's largest trading partner, India is also one of the largest providers of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Sri Lanka, with a total of around USD 2.2 billion till 2023. India's biggest investments are in energy, hospitality, real estate, manufacturing, telecommunications, banking, and financial services (Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2024). Efforts to enhance economic ties have been a priority, with discussions to restart negotiations on the Economic and Technological Cooperation Agreement (ETCA).

Infrastructure Development and Long-Term Cooperation

In 2022, Sri Lanka granted Adani Green Energy a provisional license to develop two wind projects in the Northwest Mannar and Pooneryn areas. In October 2023, Sri Lanka's state-run dairy enterprises, administered by the National Livestock Development Board, entered a joint venture with India's Amul Dairy. Discussions have begun regarding the integration of India's Adani Group into the operation of Sri Lanka's major international airports. Sri Lanka's President Ranil Wickremesinghe virtually started Phase IV of the Indian Housing Project, '*Bharat-Lanka*', in February 2024, to build 10,000 dwellings for Sri Lankan plantation workers with Indian grant aid. The same month, India launched its Unified Payment Interface in Sri Lanka, improving the financial connection between the two countries¹. As part of a bilateral debt restructuring agreement, India also decided to reduce interest rates.

Significant progress has been made in India-Sri Lanka energy cooperation, with a primary emphasis on making Trincomalee a key regional energy hub. The signing of the electrical grid interconnection agreement, which aims to facilitate cross-border power trade between the two countries and create opportunities for Sri Lanka to export excess electricity in the future, was a significant development in this regard. All Sri Lankans will profit from the agreements inked to create a multi-product pipeline and promote Trincomalee as an energy hub (Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2025).

India's and Sri Lanka's relations gain momentum with the signing of a Memorandum of Understanding on Digital Transformation Cooperation, which allows Sri Lanka to use India's digital public infrastructure models. This includes emulating India's advances in fields such as digital payments, e-governance, health technology, and citizen service delivery. In terms of health, Sri Lanka's adoption of the Indian Pharmacopoeia opens the door to increased pharmaceutical trade and healthcare collaboration (Times of India, 2025).

Security and Défense Cooperation

As India's defense engagements with other regional nations, such as the Maldives and Bangladesh, are declining, growing defense cooperation between Sri Lanka and India is becoming increasingly significant. On June 11 to June 14, 2025, Lieutenant General BKG M Lasantha Rodrigo, Commander of the Sri Lanka Army, arrived in India for an official visit. The purpose of this visit was to strengthen bilateral military cooperation and investigate potential new areas of cooperation, mainly in the areas of capability enhancement and training². Previously, India has launched capacity-building programs for Sri Lankan officers, including training at top defense institutions such as the Central Detective Training Institutes and the National Security Guard. These programs, supported by India under the Indian Technical and Economic Cooperation (ITEC) and "*Aid to Sri Lanka*" programs, are free for Sri Lankan police officers (The Hindu, 2025).

President Disanayaka praised India's defense cooperation, which included training, joint exercises, ship visits, and maritime surveillance, and thanked India for important support, such as a Dornier aircraft and a Maritime Rescue and Coordination Centre. Both sides agreed to strengthen collaboration against threats such as terrorism, drug trafficking, and money laundering through training, intelligence sharing, and capacity building, as well as to investigate a framework for defense cooperation, expand hydrographic work, supply defense platforms, and increase joint drills. They also agreed to collaborate in catastrophe mitigation and adaptive defense training. Exercise MITRA SHAKTI (with Army) was last held in Sri Lanka in August 2024, and SLINEX (Naval) occurred off Visakhapatnam, India, in December 2024 (The Hindu, 2025).

Cultural Relations

The Cultural Cooperation Agreement between India and Sri Lanka, signed in New Delhi on 29 November 1977, forms the foundation for regular cultural exchange programs between the two nations. The Indian Cultural Center in Colombo actively promotes cultural awareness by offering classes in

Indian music, dance, Hindi, and yoga (Kumar, 2023). Kathak and Bharatanatyam dance workshops, Indian classical music concerts, and film festivals showcasing Indian cinema have been organized across Sri Lanka. Sanskrit and Hindi language courses have gained popularity, strengthening linguistic and literary ties. Ayurveda and traditional medicine seminars, reflecting shared heritage, have also seen active participation from both countries. Significant cultural cooperation includes the establishment of an Indian Gallery at the International Buddhist Museum in Kandy, the restoration of the Thirukeeteswaram Temple in Mannar. The inaugural Colombo-Kushinagar flight took place on the auspicious VapPoya Day in October 2021, when the sacred Kapilavastu Buddha relics from the Rajaguru Sri Subhuthi Maha Vihara of Waskaduwa were flown to India and displayed in several Indian cities, including Kushinagar and Sarnath.

Early in 2025, India also released the Sinhala translation of Jataka Tales and the Pali grammar book Namamala. Colombo University has established the Center for Contemporary Indian Studies (CCIS). Kelaniya and Sabaragamuwa University have established a permanent ICCR chair for Hindi. The growing cultural engagement between India and Sri Lanka continues to reinforce people-to-people connections, promoting mutual understanding and appreciation of their shared traditions (Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2025).

Challenges in India–Sri Lanka Relations

Despite growing engagement, bilateral relations face structural and strategic constraints. Greater integration is resisted by Sri Lanka due to protectionist lobbying and domestic political sensitivities, which fear losing competitiveness and being economically dependent on a larger neighbour. Its capacity to gain from access to Indian markets is further restricted by a limited export portfolio, a feeble industrial base, and population constraints. These difficulties are exacerbated by non-tariff restrictions, such as on Indian clothing and pepper (Rafi, 2025). Moreover, for India, preventing foreign powers, particularly China, from taking advantage

of Sri Lanka's economic vulnerabilities to increase their influence in the Indian Ocean is India's top strategic concern. Maintaining India's 'Neighbourhood First' and SAGAR policies requires striking a balance between security requirements and economic integration. Building confidence is an ongoing task because of the complexities of South Asian geopolitics and the looking into the delicate domestic political climate in Sri Lanka.

Conclusion

India-Sri Lanka relations stand at a strategic inflection point. The Modi era has seen India's engagement with Sri Lanka move beyond traditional paradigms. It has been a period of proactive outreach, significant leveraging of soft power, and a demonstration of hard-nosed strategic assertion, especially in the context of regional competition. At the same time, under President Anura Kumara Dissanayake's tenure, cooperation offers mutual economic gains while advancing maritime security and regional stability. For India, an economically stable Sri Lanka strengthens sea lane security, bolsters regional norms of openness, and mitigates extra-regional influence in the Indo-Pacific. For Sri Lanka, India represents a reliable partner for economic recovery and diversification. In a turbulent regional environment, from Pakistan's instability to Nepal's strategic balancing, Sri Lanka presents India with an opportunity to consolidate a model of cooperative regionalism. Realising this potential will require addressing structural constraints, respecting political sensitivities, and maintaining strategic alignment. A resilient and mutually beneficial partnership could position the India–Sri Lanka relationship as a stabilising pillar in the evolving Indo-Pacific order.

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